

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE PROCESS OF CONTINUOUS SPIRITUAL EDUCATION

Baratov Bakhtiyarjon Kadyrovich

Fergana State University
independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7984551>

Annotation: In this article, opinions on increasing the activity of introducing educational standards based on a new approach to the training of future physical education teachers, on awakening a sense of responsibility for the chosen profession, on the development of various reforms in society are presented.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, continuous education, physical education teachers, innovative and digital, educational standards, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Today, the sharp increase in the flow of information, development, has led to the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, to a certain degree "obsolescence" of the existing pedagogical-psychological, methodical, practical training, and this, in turn, has led to the professional skills of those engaged in pedagogical work. , demanded that more attention should be paid to the development of creativity. One of the important factors of the implementation of this attention and demand is the introduction of technology for improving professional skills. For this, professional pedagogical training means perfecting the teaching of the fundamentals of pedagogical skills in the field of education.

It is known that there is a direct connection between general labor and professional specialization. The level of real professional skill is directly connected with the general development of a person. After all, a clear choice of a profession, gaining interest in it, awakens skillfulness. The spiritual world of a skilled professional is rich, the ability to work is deep, and with the help of his profession, he brings great benefits to himself and others. That is why the formation of professional skills, training and finally striving to improve it, filling it with the necessary information, information (knowledge), skills is an urgent issue of this day, as well as educational reforms.

The role of the teacher in society is extremely important. That is why it is not enough for a teacher to prepare to teach children, to be an educated person. First of all, he should love children, feel like a father to them, and consider everything related to their education and growth as his duty. Because a child is born with active powers by nature, it is the teacher's duty to give students the

material necessary to exercise these powers. Only when a teacher plays the role of a leader can he develop initiatives in children and arm them with knowledge. In the process of teaching students, a well-designed curriculum and a good textbook are the basis for improving the educational content. In fact, the success of education depends on the textbook, teaching methods and the teacher. A good teacher should master his subject perfectly, love his profession and children.

Professional skills include extensive knowledge about children, the organization of the educational process, its content and methods. This knowledge constitutes general pedagogical culture. If a teacher does not acquire this culture, he will never be a true master. General culture alone is not enough for a modern teacher. He observes children, compares the important things in their growth with the main social ideas that have arisen in the society, determines the ways and methods of their development, the dialectic of the transition of the methods of educational influence of different tools to each other. will have the skills of in-depth analysis, pedagogical research and scientific systematization of achievements.

Pedagogical qualification is the ability to acquire knowledge and skills of a certain type of activity and to perform it well. Such qualifications related to the activity of a teacher include the following.

A) Practical constructive skills: planning practical educational work, understanding the most important rules of activity. Creating an individual program for educating each student in a team environment. Increasing the individual attitude towards students, taking into account their youth and personal characteristics.

B) Organizational skills: ability to identify, select and perceive active children among students. To be able to organize various group and individual activities of students and to know their social activity. Establish control over the delivery of social tasks given to students and provide them with practical help when necessary. Ability to carry out practical work in a group led by him.

Knowledge of the relationship between parents and the general public. The methods of setting requirements for students are as follows: evaluation of the student's rules of conduct, knowledge of all subjects, internal rules of the college, used in the process of explanation in education. It should be noted that the duties and responsibilities of studying are to learn, practice, and teach students to work.

It is desirable for a child to study well in college, serve effectively, have a good rest, and be busy with interesting activities all the time. Requirements for

the teacher: Let both the group of students and the student clearly feel the specific goals of the activity. The implementation of the activity depends on the initiative and creative activity of teachers. In this case, it is necessary to refer to the students themselves such things as work distribution, planning, accounting, and results. The teacher guides the activities pedagogically, forms their creative habits. In the course of the activity, each child acquires performance skills. Discuss the results of the work, encourage the participants. A person's moral upbringing is manifested in various relationships with the things around him. Practical activity is an important aspect of a person's moral education system. Therefore, doing good and kindness to children is the main task of a pedagogue, not with inner experiences.

Saadi Shirozi, one of the world-famous representatives of the Eastern classical culture, is a supporter of strictness in education and education. excellent ati.

Pedagogy is distinguished from other professions by the image of teachers' thinking in "human-human" relations, their responsibility and strong sense of responsibility for the fate of students. Its main difference from other professions is the unity of its foundations, such as changing and managing a person at the same time. Considering the formation and transformation of the personality as his main goal, the pedagogue in this field undertakes to manage the mental, emotional, physical development of the student and to form a spiritual worldview.

In recent years, great efforts have been made and are being made to restore and honor the traditions, values, and religious beliefs of the nation. One of the most important works in this area is the restoration of religious values. Because today's spiritual life of the society and the long history of the Uzbek people cannot be imagined separately from the religion of Islam. Accordingly, great attention is being paid to the restoration of religious values in the society and their use in education, and to the youth's enjoyment of humanitarian and other important ideas of Islamic philosophy.

As the religion of Islam is based on enlightenment, it encourages every person to be perfect mentally and physically, to be noble and pure, and serves only goodness.

In his educational and ethical works, in which the principles of the Islamic religion are inculcated, the education of a spiritually mature person is advanced both theoretically and practically.

Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Qutadgu Bilig", Kaikovus's "Kabusnoma", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibbat-ul Haqayyq", Alishyer Navoi's "Mahbub-ul Qulub", J.Davani's "Akhlaqi Jalali", "Akhlaqi Mukhsini", Koshifi's "Futuvatnamai Sultani" " and others are among them. In all of these, the qualities characteristic of a spiritually perfect person are defined, the working people are glorified, the young generation is encouraged to acquire a profession, and the requirements and principles of the teacher-student are promoted from the point of view of the research problem.

It is no exaggeration to say that the great thinkers and scholars of the East focused all their creative activities on the formation and development of individual spirituality. After all, in Eastern countries, a child is distinguished by the fact that it is the original manifestation of spirituality.

In their views on human qualities, "evil" (ignorance) is considered a tragedy that brings death to a person. He urges people to be truthful and keep their promises. He points out three signs of a hypocrite: lying, breaking promises, and betraying trust.

He believes that the strength of a person is not in physical strength, but in the ability to control oneself when angry. Universal human values such as a stable, peaceful family environment, healthy and well-fed family members, respect for children and elders are reflected in his works. In particular, "Whoever wants to live a prosperous life and leave a good name in the world, should be kind to his relatives and always be aware of their condition."

Universal, moral values such as "a stable, peaceful family environment, healthy and well-fed family members, respect for children, respect for adults..." are reflected in his works.

Hadith scholar Allama al-Tirmizi has many hadiths that encourage people to be united, to benefit the community, and to be friends and brotherhood. Alloma, following the folk saying that "a healthy mind lives in a healthy body", urges to take care of health from a young age and not to waste time.

The encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni in his teachings tells students that they should protect their hearts from bad vices, situations that a person cannot perceive, hardened customs, anger, greed, and fame. He knew that the main cause of all evils is ignorance. He emphasizes the role of a person's desire for knowledge, interest and social environment in the acquisition of knowledge. Beruni uses pride in the sense of good manners and says in his book "Relics of Ancient Nations": "Pride is in fact the priority of good manners and noble deeds, acquisition of knowledge and wisdom, and purification from existing impurities

as much as possible. Whoever has these qualities, the judgment will be in his favor, and whoever lacks them, the judgment will be against him." Beruni emphasizes that three things are important in human maturity. This is the current enlightenment, which also recognizes science - heredity, social environment and proper education. According to Beruni, the important factors of a person's maturity are having a lot of knowledge and high morals.

Ibn Sina, like other thinkers, expressed his views on the perfect person in connection with his philosophical and social thoughts. Let's talk about the scientist's views on "perfect human education" in his work. Abu Ali ibn Sina calls for the acquisition of knowledge, which is the first criterion for reaching maturity. The reason for this is that science reveals the laws of nature and society and conveys them to generations. He says that in order to achieve this goal, a person should not be afraid of the difficulties he will face. Hey brothers: The hero of the people is not afraid of problems. He who refuses to mature is the most cowardly of men." Because an educated person is brave, he is not afraid of death, he works only to know the truth, he says, continuing his thought. Ibn Sina points out that the environment surrounding him is of special importance in the formation of a person, and this environment affects not only the knowledge of the world around him, but also the formation of positive or negative aspects in his behavior. Therefore, he believes that it is necessary to be careful in raising children, to keep them away from a bad social environment. No matter which of Ibn Sina's works on education and morals, we are sure that these works are of great importance in the education and upbringing of our mature generations, in making them wise, knowledgeable and strong enough to meet the demands of the times. In the teachings of Yusuf Khos Hajib, a mature thinker, the issues of human perfection and perfection have a large place. The scientist's most famous "Kutadgu Bilig" (Knowledge that Leads to Bliss) is a mature educational work on education that educates people to be perfect in all aspects, and its advice is a work that leads young people to perfection in the truest sense. Moral qualities are glorified in the work - humanity, truthfulness, trust, honesty, purity, love, loyalty, honesty, loyalty, intelligence, honesty, etc.

Enlighteners who made a great contribution to the development of national spiritual-educational, political views and scientific knowledge through their activities, scientific and educational heritage, also through works that are considered a component of scientific-cultural heritage, national-spiritual wealth who expressed their spiritual-educational and moral views.

Encyclopedist Ahmed Donish enriched his teachings about the spiritual education and enlightenment of the peoples of the East with new ideas in his works such as "History of the Emirs of Bukhara", "Navodirul vaqoye", (Rare events). In the work "Rare events" he emphasizes that the basis of human happiness and spiritual and moral perfection is work. The work "Bequest to children. In the chapter entitled "On the benefits of profession and craft", the scholar encourages young people to learn a craft.

As Abdulla Awlani in his work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" in his content-rich and colorful teaching about spirituality and enlightenment, spirituality is not only a mental state characteristic of a person, but also society, state, nation. , is also the main factor of personal development and maturity. So, spirituality is a characteristic of a person, it is formed on the basis of the inheritance and example of generations, knowledge, manners, education and upbringing, and it gives a purpose and direction to a person's life and activities, - says alloma.[1]

In his views, Abdulla Awlani pays special attention to the issue of behavior that represents the spiritual image of a person. The idea that spiritual education is of primary importance in the formation of a human personality has a significant place in the scientific and pedagogical heritage of the enlightened scientist.

It is known that education includes the process of teaching and all educational activities. Only when upbringing is combined with education, it becomes the basis for mature spirituality. Abdulla Awlani, noting that the importance of education in the spiritual and moral maturity of a person is incomparable: "Education is a matter of life or death for us, or salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster", [2:35]. Thus, when looking at the history of education, the Uzbek people, including scholars, in their educational heritage, the spiritual education of the young generation, in particular, the process of continuous spiritual education, is important even for the current era. It is possible to be sure that they put forward the views.

Today, a number of scientific and research works have been carried out in this field. In the research conducted by T. Mahmudov, the main emphasis is on the spirituality of the individual and the views on the circumstances that reflect it in the process of its formation. T. Mahmudov interprets the concept of "Spirituality" as follows: "Spirituality represents the "mind and heart" of an individual and a nation, according to the requirements of history, it is a spiritual

perception that expresses the degree of humanization of nature and man. [3:114]

Professor B. Ziyomukhamedov defines spirituality as follows: "Spirituality is a set of creative qualities that a person's acquired useful knowledge has been tested in his practical life, has passed the level of skills and qualifications, and is absorbed into his soul and reflected in his lifestyle." [4:14]

Tilab Makhmudov believes that "spirituality - ... finds a place in the mind and heart, becomes concrete in the light world in the form of a spiritual value, becomes visible only when it is materialized and humanized. Whatever the needs of a particular society and nation are prioritized by a person, these things gain more importance in the world of spirituality. That is the historicity of spirituality. As a product of the people of the infinite soul, it has its eternal and eternal characteristics. [5]

The main direction of scientific research carried out by teacher, scientist O. Musurmonova is the problem of formation of spiritual culture among high school students of general secondary schools. Pedagogical conditions, factors with significant influence, criteria determining the level of formation of the student's spirituality are discussed [6]. According to O. Musurmonova, two stages are important in the formation of the student's spirituality. They are:

- to create an environment that serves as a foundation for the formation of spiritual culture among high school students of general secondary schools;
- creating conditions that allow students to organize spiritual activities:
- spiritual understanding.

O. Musurmonova emphasizes that the unity between the mentioned factors is a model for forming the spiritual culture of high school students by means of spiritual values.[7]

Professional training of teachers-pedagogues V.A.Slastenin, polytechnic training of teacher-pedagogues Y.K.Vasilev, training of future teachers for pedagogical technologies V.P.Bespalko, training of labor and vocational education teachers in scientific pedagogical literature it is stated that the methodological complex was researched by A.R. Khodzhaboyev,[12] the formation of the personality of a labor education teacher by U.N. Nishonaliyev, the professional formation of a future vocational education teacher by N.A. Muslimov and others.

In this sense, the following are important in preparing future teachers for continuous spiritual education.

1. Pedagogical requirements;

2. Axiological factors;
3. Modern needs.

Aptitude is the primary basis for pedagogical requirements, skill for axiological factors, and competence for contemporary needs. The embodiment of these forms the requirements for the formation of spiritual education in students. In this way, the teacher appears as a collective subject carrying social knowledge and values and an individual subject carrying out pedagogical activities.

In the conditions of a democratic society and a market economy, students' tasks are expanding and, as a result, their responsibilities are increasing. In this sense, it is becoming necessary that students' spiritual education meets modern needs and improves in the process of education.

For this reason, special attention is being paid to the requirements of young people. Because in order to satisfy and respond to such demands, spiritual education is formed in students and young people. Patriotism, knowledge and modernity are important as components of training future teachers for the process of continuous spiritual education. The structure of these components can be defined as follows.

Currently, the adoption of such components in the system of preparing students of higher educational institutions for continuous spiritual education is not without reasons. Because it is the Motherland, Knowledge, and Time factors that meet the demands and needs of future teachers. For example, a number of requirements are set for the student in the regulatory and legal documents related to education, or many approaches are described in scientific research. However, all of them comply with the requirements established by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education".

In our opinion, these requirements can be set even today in the preparation of future teachers for the process of continuous spiritual education. Because continuous spiritual education is formed by means of spiritual, social and professional requirements imposed by the society. For example, the requirements that make up the composition of maturity represent pedagogical and psychological requirements, and the composition of patriotism represents the requirements of training and effective activity. These requirements stated by Alisher Navoi are the product of the development of our society.

It follows from this approach that in the process of continuous spiritual education, students should be trained on the basis of concrete and real situations in order to acquire maturity, spiritual perfection and social activity in

the formation of concepts of patriotism, love of the motherland, preservation of it, prosperity and independence. is appropriate. In this sense, the psychological principles of the formation of spiritual education in students should have an encouraging and adaptive nature. This means that maturity, spiritual maturity, and social activity are states (levels) that are first of all acquired through spiritual-spiritual adaptation, aspiration, and adaptation.

References:

1. Abdullah Awlani. Turkish culture or morality.-T.: Teacher, 1992. -V. 58.
2. Abdullah Awlani. Turkish culture or morality.-T.: Teacher, 1992. -V. 35.
3. Makhmudov T. About Avesta. T.: Sharq, 2000: -V. 117.
4. Zunnunov A. History of pedagogy. -T.: Teacher, 2004. -V. 8.
5. Makhmudov T. About Avesta. T.: Sharq, 2000: -V. 14
6. Musurmonova O. Formation of students' spiritual culture. - T.: Science, 1998. - V. 56
7. Musurmonova O. Formation of students' spiritual culture. - T.: Science, 1998. - V. 26
8. Mahkamov U. Moral and etiquette lessons. - T.: Science, 1998.-V. 15
9. Mavlonova R. et al. Pedagogy. Textbook. -T.: Teacher, 2001.-V. 26
10. Shodiev N. The first source of natural sciences (based on the written record "Avesta") // "Ziyokor" magazine, 2001, issue 9. -V. 38-41.
- 11.Сластенин В.А. Формирование личности учителя советской школы в процессе профессиональной подготовке. -М.: Просвещение, 1976.-159 с.
- 12.Васильев Ю.К. Политехническая подготовка ученика средней школы. – М.: Педагогика, 1978. – 175с.
- 13.Беспалько В.П., Татур Ю.Г. Системно-методическое обеспечение учебновоспитательного процесса подготовки специалистов. – М.: Высшая школа, 1989. – 144с
14. Yusupov E. Values and their role in the life of society.-T.: University, 1996.
- 15.Нишоналиев У.Н. Формирование личности учителя трудового обучения: проблемы и перспективы. -Т.: Фан, 1990.-86 с.
16. Muslimov N.A. Theoretical and methodological bases of professional formation of a teacher of vocational education. 13.00.08-Theory and methodology of vocational education. Dissertation written for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. -Tashkent, 2007.-315 p.